

Let's talk FAIR: (Re)using FAIR vocabularies and schemas in humanities and social sciences research

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Introduction

To improve the visibility, transparency, and impact of research, also to fit the bigger aims of doing open science, researchers are increasingly encouraged to make their data findable and accessible, as well as to reuse existing schemas or vocabularies to make their data connected and interoperable with the wider data ecosystem. For this purpose, researchers are commonly advised to (re)use existing controlled vocabularies¹.

However, it is not always clear to researchers how, in practice, they can (re)use existing vocabularies and schemas, or how to make their own publicly readable for transparency or reuse. Moreover, even if a researcher in one domain may be familiar with a vocabulary in her/his specific domain, this person may not be aware of a vocabulary in other domains, which could also be relevant.

For that purpose, the CLARIAH infrastructure project², continued by SSHOC-NL³, began in 2022 the construction of a **FAIR vocabulary registry** to gather vocabularies produced and used by the social sciences and humanities research communities (SSH) in the Netherlands and in wider networks such as CLARIN-ERIC⁴ and ODISSEI⁵. This registry (<https://registry.vocabs.clariah.nl/>) is currently functional and actively developed as part of the roadmap for The Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud for the Netherlands (Dykstra et al., 2023).

¹ See for example the research guides from DANS (<https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl/>) or Utrecht University (<https://www.uu.nl/en/research/research-data-management/tools/fair-cheatsheets-to-publish-your-research-data-and-software-fair>)

² <https://www.clariah.nl/>

³ <https://sshoc.nl/>

⁴ <https://www.clarin.eu/>

⁵ <https://odissei-data.nl/>

For this reason, we would like to propose a workshop to the DH Benelux community, to make humanities researchers aware of the existence of the FAIR vocabulary registry and to involve them in its active use and improvement. Two of the authors of this DHBenelux workshop proposal have been direct creators of this registry (Meijer and Windhouwer, 2024), and the other co-authors of the workshop proposal are taking part in improving its code, content, and promoting its use among the community of researchers.

The workshop doesn't require previous technical knowledge, and it will cover different aspects around the FAIR vocabulary registry, such as the principles of creating, sharing and (re) using FAIR vocabularies, some details about how the registry was built, how the vocabularies are selected and curated, and how scholars can connect their tacit, theoretical, or practical knowledge of taxonomies, thesauri, ontologies, metadata schemas, code books, and qualitative coding to the FAIR vocabularies principles and practices.

Background and scientific scope

Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain are numerous and dissimilar due to the variety of domains that are encompassed under this umbrella. SSHOC-NL lists for example “economics, sociology, psychology, media studies, linguistics, literature, art history, heritage science, history, communication sciences, political science” as part of the disciplines covered by the SSH domain (Dykstra et al., 2023). Besides this disparity in their subjects, the practice of sharing and reusing vocabularies in the SSH is less common than the sciences (for example, in the biomedical domain) where there are common practices and mature systems to share vocabularies⁶.

This doesn't mean that SSH researchers are not creating and using vocabularies, but they are often re(created) anew for each research project, or published in ways that don't facilitate reuse (for example as “code books” added as appendices to scholarly publications or, in the best cases, added as documentation to accompany their datasets). Besides, there is in the SSH domain what Mourits et al. (2025) described as a paradoxical situation of scholars needing a common language, necessary to make larger-scale comparisons possible, but at the same time being hesitant to apply schemes not designed for a specific social, spatial, and temporal context (Mourits et al., p.2).

The need to have an overview of which vocabularies exist within a discipline or domain has already existed for a couple of decades. A historical review of these attempts to inventorize different types of vocabularies is included in Golub et al. (2014), who found efforts to list existing thesauri already from the end of the 1980's and beginning of the 1990's. Some vocabulary registries already exist which could be used in the SSH; for example: the Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) registry has been on air since ca. 2013, with a focus on providing access to vocabularies which are published as linked open data (<https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov>); active registries such as Bartoc⁷ are a very comprehensive way to find and access vocabularies

⁶ See for example: <https://ontoportal.org>

⁷ <https://bartoc.org/>

from different domains and countries, but this level of generalization makes it more distant to the practices of the SSH community; or the DARIAH vocabulary registry (<https://vocabs.dariah.eu/en/>), which aims to inventorize vocabularies used in the humanities, which makes it become narrow to for the Social Science domain.

In sum, different factors have led to the creation of the **(CLARIAH) FAIR vocabulary registry** in the previous years: the drive to encourage FAIR and open science, the example from other domains in publishing and reusing vocabularies, and the need to provide an inventory and specific support for (re)using existing vocabularies in the SSH, which to date has only been partially covered.

The FAIR vocabulary registry

The FAIR vocabulary registry is currently functional and in active development. Figure1 shows its current graphic-user interface, and Figure2 shows its system architecture.

The screenshot displays the SSH FAIR Vocabulary Registry interface. At the top, a dark blue header contains the site name and navigation links: About, Guidelines, FAQ, HowTos, Release notes, and Publications. Below the header, the main content area is divided into several sections. On the left, there is a 'TEXT SEARCH' section with a search input field and a 'Search' button. Below this are four filter categories: SYNTAX (owl (29), rdfs (8), skos (3)), TYPE (ontology (32), list (3), thesaurus (2), authority file (1), gazetteer (1)), ENTITY (Concept (26), Person (6), Place (2), Time-Span (2), Event-Activity (1), Organisation (1)), and TOPIC (NWO) (Librarianship, archive studies (4), Linguistics (4), History (3), Geography (2)). The main content area shows '40 results, page 1 of 4 pages' and a 'Register new vocabulary' button. Below this, there are three featured vocabulary entries: 'AGROVOC Core' (owl), 'An ontology about letter corresponding' (rdfs), and 'Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)' (owl). Each entry includes a brief description and a 'Show more' button. The 'AGROVOC Core' entry describes it as a multilingual and controlled vocabulary designed to cover concepts and terminology under FAO's areas of interest. The 'An ontology about letter corresponding' entry is a formal description of letter corresponding, related classes, and properties. The 'Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)' entry is a small, upper level ontology designed for use in supporting information retrieval, analysis and integration in scientific and other domains. The 'Brick: A uniform metadata schema for buildings' entry (rdfs) is an open-source effort to standardize semantic descriptions of the physical, logical and virtual.

Figure1. FAIR vocabulary registry's current graphic user search and browsing interface (<https://registry.vocabs.clariah.nl/>, version 2025-06-03)

The current architecture of the FAIR vocabulary registry is outlined in Figure 2: to register the vocabulary-level metadata the “Component Metadata Infrastructure” (CMDI)⁸ is used to create a metadata profile defining the required elements, and an editor facilitating metadata management. Each vocabulary description adheres to this CMDI profile, serving as the input for the vocabulary workers⁹. These workers perform a number of tasks, such as caching vocabulary objects (in a SPARQL store). The registry itself is also written in Python as an API service, complemented by a web graphic user interface (GUI)¹⁰. Leveraging data from the SPARQL store, the registry empowers users to explore and search through the vocabularies. Furthermore, the vocabulary recommender¹¹ is a tool that also utilizes both the stored vocabulary metadata and the vocabularies within the SPARQL store to recommend specific vocabularies based on user search queries. (Windhouwer & Meijer, 2024).

(FAIR vocabulary registry’s architecture, Windouwer & Meijer, 2024)

Before the conference in June 2025, the registry will be more mature and ready to be widely presented to the user community and used in real research scenarios. Some of the improvements that we are currently working on are:

- Improving the vocabulary-level metadata to include more facets (KOS type, themes, NWO research areas, among others).
- Adding more vocabularies in consultation with SHHOC.NL task leaders.
- Connecting each vocabulary to other existing vocabulary registries (e.g., LOV, Bartoc, Oddissei, etc.)
- Creating a project home page and adding technical and user documentation.
- Collecting guidelines and practical instructions for researchers and curators about how to create and (re)use vocabularies.
- Improving the metrics for FAIR assessments.

⁸ <https://www.clarin.eu/content/cmd-i-component-metadata-infrastructure>

⁹ <https://github.com/CLARIAH/vocab-workers>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/CLARIAH/vocab-registry>

¹¹ <https://recommender.vocabs.dev.clariah.nl/>

Workshop proposal

Workshop's aims

The aims of the workshop are:

- 1) To introduce the participants to the general principles of creating, sharing and re(using) FAIR vocabularies in SSH research.
- 2) To explain the functionality of the FAIR vocabulary registry and guide participants on how to use it for their own research projects.
- 3) To share practical knowledge on how to create their own vocabularies and schemas (via application profiles).
- 4) To engage participants in identifying potentially interesting vocabularies to add and explain how they are added to the registry (curation process).
- 5) To encourage vocabulary creators to use the FAIR principles explaining the metrics for FAIR assessments (and what does this mean in practice).

Workshop's length

To cover all topics in detail and give enough time for hands-on practice, we propose a full day-workshop.

Note to the organizers: the length of the workshop depends on the number of participants who register, we would like to provide a registration form in which they choose which theme is interesting for them, and in which we gather input about their knowledge and expectations. Depending on that, we can merge or leave out some of the proposed slots below to make the workshop tailored to the audience.

Number of participants

Maximum 25

Researchers, data managers, curators and developers are welcome. They don't need to have previous knowledge of FAIR vocabularies, technical expertise, or knowledge from a specific subject domain.

Preliminary program

9 - 9.30: Welcome coffee/tea

9.30 - 10.45: Introduction

- *general principles of FAIR vocabularies*
- *demo of the main parts/functionality of the FAIR vocabulary registry*

- *demo on how vocabularies are selected and curated.*
- *Similarities, differences and complementarities with the NDE Termennetwerk and other registries.*

10.45-11.00: Break

11.-12.30: Hands-on searching and browsing vocabularies using the FAIR vocabulary registry.

- *Participants work on their own or in small groups searching and browsing vocabularies for their own research or project(s).*
- *We provide a questionnaire for usability evaluation to gather feedback about the functionality of the FAIR vocabulary registry and/or to get suggestions for missing vocabularies that we could integrate in the future.*

12.30-13.30: Lunch

13:30-15:00: Adapting vocabularies and schemas (a step-by-step tutorial)

- *We demonstrate, with some examples, how to use a vocabulary once you find it*
- *We demonstrate how to adapt and create vocabularies for your own research using application profiles*
- *If time allows: we show or provide links or guidance on how to create your own vocabulary and publish it as SKOS.*

15.00 - 15.15: Break

15:15 -16:30: Break out groups:

- *Group 1 (Querying vocabularies with SPARQL)*
- *Group 2 (FAIR metrics/ assessments)*

16:30 - 16:45: Break

16:45-17:00 Closing remarks

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- NKOS Consolidated Workshop 2023:

<https://nkos.dublincore.org/2023NKOSworkshop/NKOS2023.html>